

THE EFFECT OF THERMAL CYCLING AND FATIGUE LOADING ON THE PROPERTIES OF ALUMINIUM-BORON FIBRE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of thermal cycling of AlCu4Mg-B fiber composite material (CM) on its mechanical properties was studied between room temperature and maximum temperature of 400 and 500°C followed by fatigue symmetrical bending loading. Expressive degradation of mechanical properties of CM was observed after thermocycling at 500°C and was attributed to chemical reaction at the interface between fiber and matrix which predominantly lowers the strength of reinforcing fibres. Optical and electron microscopy were also utilized to observe thermal and fatigue damage which occurred as radial cracks or separation the matrix from the fiber surface. These defects do not primarily cause the degradation of CM strength.

Keywords: composite material, thermocycling, fatigue

1. INTRODUCTION

Some of engineering parts made of composite materials (CM) can be used at the alternating temperature and loading as for example the blades of compressor working at the temperatures from -60 to 380°C. They are loaded on bending and torsion. For these purposes the CM possessing high specific strength and high specific Young's modulus can be convenient. Given requirements can be fulfilled by aluminium based CM strengthened by boron fibres. The lack of Al-B CM is its chemical instability at the phase interface at higher temperature. New phase arising on fibre surface lowers its mechanical properties and thus also the properties of CM. Technology of material production, working temperature and mode of loading can affect the formation of this phase.

The aim of the present work is to find out the influence of thermal cycling and fatigue symmetrical bending loading on the properties of CM made of AlCu4Mg alloy reinforced on both sides by two monolayers composed of AlMg3 and B fibers. Failure mechanism of this material is studied.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENT

CM consisted of AlCu4Mg alloy sheet of 1 mm thickness strengthened on both sides by two monolayers with unidirectionally aligned B fibres of diameter of 0,14 mm. The arrangement of compo-

nents of CM is shown in Figure 1. The strength of fiber, matrix and CM are in Table 1. Samples were prepared by hot pressing in vacuum at the temperature of 480°C, pressure of 15 MPa and duration of 900 s [1]. The thickness of the samples was about 1,5 mm and fiber volume amount in monolayer was 60 % and fiber volume amount in CM as a whole was 20 vol%. Tensile strength of CM is equal to theoretical strength given by rule of mixture. (Table 1).

Samples were exposed to cycle loading at the temperature of 400 and 500°C with 300,600 and 900 cycles. The shape of thermal cycles is shown in Figure 2. Influence of thermal cycling on the fiber properties separated from the matrix as well as on the properties of CM were determined. The process was studied by optical and electron microscopy as well as by acoustic emission.

d)

b)

Figure 1. Arrangement of CM, components. 1-monolayer of CM reinforced by B fibers, 2-AlCu4Mg matrix

Figure 2. Shape of thermal cycles

After thermal cycling the SCHENK PWOG instrument was used for room temperature fatigue testing using symmetrical bending frequency of 23 Hz. The failure mechanism of samples and degradation of their properties were studied.

Table 1. Experimental and theoretical strength R_m before and after thermal cycling. (M, F, CM, t are for matrix, fiber, composite material, theoretical, respectively).

Strength MPa	As received	After thermal cycling							
		$T^{\circ}\text{C}: 300$ $N_c: 900$	300	400 600	900	300	500 600	900	
R_{mM}	253	187	239	221	180	160	106	90	
R_{mF}	2750	2970	2725	2478	1985	1570	1542	1404	
R_{mCM}	746	740	733	709	610	513	462	394	
R_{mCMt}	752	744	736	671	541	442	392	352	
R_{mCMt}/R_{mCM}	1,008	1,005	1,004	.946	.886	.861	.848	.893	
R_{mCM} Fatigue limit	580	-	-	510	-	-	355	200	

Values R_{mM} are from [2]

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Thermal cycling tests were done for two highest temperatures (400 and 500°C). Properties of CM after thermal cycling at 300°C are not changing up to 900 cycles neither by isothermal heating up to 1000 h [2]. Measured values of the strength of components and of CM at the cycling temperature of 400 and 500°C after 300, 600 and 900 cycles are in Table 1 and the decrease of the strength is shown in Figure 3. Dependence of the strength of separated fibers is similar to that of CM. Degradation of the properties of CM after thermal cycling is manifested also in fatigue test for symmetrical bending at room temperature. Wohler's curves after thermal cycling are shown in Figure 4. Considerable lowering of fatigue strength can be seen for temperature of 500°C after 900 cycles.

Figure 3. Dependence of tensile strength of CM after thermal cycling at 400 and 500°C on the number of cycles.

Figure 4. Wohler's curves of CM after thermal cycling. Thermocyc.: 1-none, 2-400°C, 600 c; 3-500°C, c; 4-500°C, 900 cycles.

4. DISCUSSION

In CM whose components have different coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE), as in our case, where CTE of AlCu4Mg alloy is $\alpha_M = 21,4 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ and that of B filament is $\alpha_F = 2,4 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$, during its heating and cooling the internal stresses occur with changing signs. The highest value they reach at the fiber-matrix interface. Their character is longitudinal (in fiber direction), radial (across the fiber direction) and circumferential [3]. Theoretical values of these stresses were calculated after [4,5] taking into account variable values of the elastic constants and CTEs in dependence on the temperature [6]. In many cases these values are higher than matrix yield strength. From this results that the plastic deformation of the matrix after thermal cycling at the temperature we used, starts close to the phase interface. Thermal cycling is low cycle fatigue accompanied with elastic and plastic deformation and with time depending relaxation. Taking into account the shape of thermal cycles (Figure 2) with zero dwell time at the upper and lower temperature the relaxation process can be neglected.

Plastic deformation occurring due to thermocycling leads to cumulation of defects in CM which are then responsible for crack ini-

tiation at the phase interface. The cracks occur due to the radial and circumferential stresses whose calculated values are higher (around 32 MPa at 500°C) than the value of longitudinal stresses (around 17 MPa at 500°C). Owing to that at the interface the cracks preferentially arise in the matrix along the fibre and a separation of matrix from the fiber surface occurs, Figure 5. These cracks can

Figure 5. Separation of matrix from fiber and radial cracks on fracture surface of a specimen after thermal cycling at 500°C for 300 cycles

Figure 7. Brittle fracture without pulling out of fibres. Specimen thermal cycled at 500°C for 600 cycles.

Figure 6. Time dependence of stress (σ)-1, deformation (ϵ)-2 and acoustic emission event counts (N_{AE})-3 for specimens after thermal cycling at a) 400°C, 600 cycles; b) 500°C, 600 cycles.

contribute to the degradation of CM strength. Stronger influence on the change of CM strength has the degradation of fiber strength. The fibers are in a thermocycling process deformed elastically and longitudinal stresses are insufficient (their calculated values are around 200 MPa) to nucleate the microcracks on their surface. Degradation of fiber properties is due to the rise of chemical reaction

on the fiber surface. Product of chemical reaction are new phases of $(Al, Mg)B_2$, $\alpha-AlB_{12}$ and $\beta-AlB_{12}$. Forming new phases at the temperature of $400^\circ C$ takes longer time, for temperature of $500^\circ C$ it is immediate. The existence of phases at mentioned temperature were confirmed in [2]. New phases are brittle and owing to the deformation they are the source of microcracks which are responsible for degradation of fiber strength and thus also of CM strength.

Acoustic emission (AE) analysis of tensile tested specimen after thermal cycling has shown differences in number of AE events N_{AE} in dependence on the temperature. The specimen cycled at $400^\circ C$ have high AE event counts in comparison with specimen cycled at $500^\circ C$, Figure 6. In the process of tensile deformation of specimen cycled at $400^\circ C$ (Figure 6a) the defects are initiating in a broad deformation interval. These defects cause the fracture in the last phase of deformation. Fracture has tough character with the pull out the fibers from matrix. In the case of specimen cycled at $500^\circ C$ after the initiation of the first defects the fracture starts at small deformation (Figure 6b). Character of fracture surface is brittle without pulling out the fibres (Figure 7.)

Figure 8. Delamination of surface reinforcing layers from matrix in the process of fatigue on bending after $N=10^6$ cycles. Specimen thermal cycled at $400^\circ C$ for 600 cycles.

Figure 9. Multiple fiber fracture close to the place of specimen failure. Specimen after thermal cycling at $400^\circ C$, 600 cycles

Defects occurring in the matrix and in the fiber during thermocycling considerably affect the fatigue strength after symmetrical bending loading at room temperature (Figure 4). Fatigue limit decreases with temperature and number of cycles. Decreasing of fatigue limit is especially expressive at thermocycling temperature of $500^\circ C$. Fatigue limit of specimens after thermocycling at $400^\circ C$ for 600 cycles decreases about 22 % and at $500^\circ C$ for 600 cycles about 40 % in comparison with specimen without thermocycling. For specimen cycled at $500^\circ C$ for 900 cycles the fatigue limit decreases about 65 % (Figure 4). The reinforcing monolayers at the beginning starts to separate due to bending loading from the matrix (Figure 8). In course of fatigue test the failure of all fibers is very rarely. From this reason it is not possible to study the fracture surface after fatigue. Close to the failure of specimen multiplied fracture of fi-

bers starts as can be seen on longitudinal section of surface monolayer (Figure 9).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results can be summarized as follows:

-During the thermocycling process at the temperature of 400°C and 500°C the internal stresses occur at the fiber-matrix interface (longitudinal, radial and circumferential). Owing to these stresses the defects are cumulating in the matrix close to phase interface and due to defects transversal and longitudinal cracks are initiated and separation of fibre from matrix occurs.

-At the temperature of 400°C and 900 cycles the chemical interaction starts between the matrix and the fiber surface resulting in forming of new phases of $(Al.Mg)B_2$, $\alpha-AlB_{12}$ and $\beta-AlB_{12}$. At the temperature of 500°C the forming of brittle phase is more expressive. Due to these phases there is a strong degradation of fiber strength and thus the degradation of resulting CM. Degradation of fiber strength has the main effect on the lowering of CM strength.

-Acoustic emission analysis confirms different character of defect initiation at the studied temperatures of cycling. The mode of fracture is different too.

-Fatigue symmetric bending tests showed degradation of fatigue limit in dependence on cycling temperature (for 400 °C and higher) and number of cycles.

-It has been confirmed that studied CM keeps its mechanical properties to the temperature lower than 400°C.

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